

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

Yuldasheva Dilbar Saidakhmedovna¹

¹ English teacher of academic lyceum of TSTU

dilbaryuldashevateacher@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5866255>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 07th January 2022

Accepted: 12th January 2022

Online: 17th January 2022

KEY WORDS

speaking skill, speech exercises, concept of "speaking", cultural and national characteristics

ABSTRACT

This article is compiled in order to summarize ideas about the issue of improving speaking skill in the context of learning foreign languages, to present the main problems faced by teachers when improving this skill, as well as to provide ways to achieve this task by presenting some types of tasks and speech exercises.

Speaking is an effective type of speech activity, thanks to which communication is carried out. This type of speech activity can be characterized by such signs as: close interaction with the personality and with the speech function of thinking, the presence of a goal, motivation. Teaching speaking in a foreign language lesson aims to form such speech skills that would give the student the opportunity to use them in everyday speech practice at the level of habitual everyday communication. The key role in improving speaking skills is played not only by speech exercises, but also by the skills of working with text, analyzing video and audio materials, using the case method.

In order to realize this goal, it is necessary to develop the following communicative skills and abilities in students:

a) to be aware of and create foreign utterances depending on a certain

communicative situation, communicative intention and speech task.

b) to implement their verbal and non-verbal behavior, taking into account the principles of communication, as well as the cultural and national characteristics of the country of the language being studied;

c) use appropriate means of learning a foreign language, develop the habit of independently improving the language.

Not the last place on the way to mastering a foreign language is occupied by the formation of certain properties of language learners, which contribute to a more effective process of language formation as a means of intercultural communication. Here we are talking about the development of students:

-interest and positive attitude to the language, to the culture of the people who speak this language;

-awareness of oneself as a person belonging to a specific cultural and linguistic community;

-education of consciousness in learning a foreign language;

-the need for self-education.

Each speech skill contains in its core certain actions brought to automatism through the previous repeated performance of various exercises. Each exercise is selected based on the level of training of the student. The main place here is given to the so-called (speech) communicative exercises, the purpose of which is to form certain skills and communication skills as close as possible to real conditions.

Their goal:

- teach you to clearly state the main idea;

- summarize the content using the accumulated speech experience and various associations as a basis;

- it is logical to form thoughts;

- develop the ability to paraphrase - i.e. explain the same phenomenon /object / property in different words.

All these exercises are a multi-level system, while the formation of communication skills (the ultimate goal of which, again, is free speaking) is directly related to the creation of two types of exercises:

1) for the development of prepared speech (speech that can be controlled by a teacher). To form such speech, students

mainly use memory, associative connections and various supports.

2) for the formation of skills of unprepared speech (speech that the teacher cannot control). In comparison with prepared speech, it is a more complex action, since it assumes the ability of the student to perform communication tasks without preparation (on the spot), using the language base accumulated during training.

An unprepared speech, in any case, should be formed after the stage of formation of a prepared speech.

The stage of improving the prepared speech.

1. Transformation of the source text (taken as a sample).

2. Creating your own statement:

a) by means of verbal supports (plan, theses, keywords, headings);

b) relying on visual aids (source of information: pictures, movies, magazines);

c) Based on the topic already covered.

Summing up, it is important to recall that when forming speaking skills in any foreign language, it is fundamentally important that the education process be conducted in a foreign language, while not focusing only on the problems of the language. This should be a comprehensive approach involving varying the topic of the lesson, which always follows the purpose of the lesson. Each lesson should focus on one primary task, while the others only complement it.

REFERENCES:

1. Claire Elizabeth. "ESL teachers' activities kit". Prentice Hall Direct. New Jersey. 1998
2. Jack Richards. "Designing instructional materials for teaching listening comprehension", in "The Language Teaching Matrix". Cambridge. 1990
3. Murtha Sheila & Jane Airey O'Connor. "English the American Way: A Fun ESL Guide to Language & Culture in the U.S.". Research & Education Association. Washington. 2011